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Afghanistan at the Crossroads of the Green Transition: China, Critical Minerals, and the New Extractive Frontier

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Abstract

Objective: This study examines Afghanistan's emerging role within the global political economy of critical minerals, with particular focus on how Chinese engagement under the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) reshapes extractive governance in a post-conflict, institutionally fragile state. **Method:** Drawing on a qualitative political economy approach, the analysis integrates four complementary theoretical frameworks like the Uneven and Combined Development (UCD), the Resource Curse thesis, Dependency Theory, and Chinese state capitalism to assess how global structural forces intersect with Afghan institutional fragilities. Primary data collected through semi-structured interviews with three Afghan policy specialists, conducted in Dari and back-translated into Portuguese, supplement documentary and secondary sources. **Conclusion:** The study concludes that, while Chinese investment offers short-term fiscal benefits, it ultimately reinforces long-term structural dependency and amplifies environmental vulnerability. The case demonstrates that the global green transition, despite its ostensibly sustainable aims, can perpetuate extractive hierarchies, making Afghanistan a critical site for evaluating the contradictions of state-led development and the governance of critical minerals in the Global South.

Keywords: Peripheral Economies; Belt and Road Initiative; Critical Mineral Extraction; Green Extractivism; Afghanistan.

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Introduction

Afghanistan occupies a strategic position at the crossroads of Central, South, and West Asia, bordering major regional powers including China, Iran, and Pakistan. This geographical centrality endows the country with significant geopolitical value as both a land bridge and a historical fault line in global politics. Beneath its rugged terrain lies an extraordinary concentration of mineral resources: preliminary United States Geological Survey assessments (USGS, 2011), identified deposits valued at more than one trillion US dollars, encompassing copper, lithium, iron, cobalt, and rare earth elements (REEs). These resources have acquired growing strategic significance in a global context that prioritizes the energy transition and advanced manufacturing.

Lithium reserves, concentrated primarily in the provinces of Helmand, Ghazni, and Nuristan, have attracted particular attention given their essential role in battery production for electric vehicles and renewable energy storage systems (IEA, 2023). A 2010 Pentagon assessment famously characterized Afghanistan as potentially "the Saudi Arabia of lithium"—a label that, while evocative, also reflects the geopolitical projections of external powers onto uncertain geological realities (The New York Times, 2010).

Despite this geological wealth, Afghanistan remains one of the poorest countries in the world. Its economy continues to rely heavily on subsistence agriculture, remittances, and humanitarian assistance. Decades of armed conflict, compounded by entrenched governance weaknesses, pervasive corruption, and abrupt political ruptures, have systematically undermined efforts to build stable institutions. As a result, the mineral sector contributes less than two percent of gross domestic product (World Bank, 2023). Rather than generating developmental gains, natural resources have repeatedly served as instruments of political capture, financing armed factions and perpetuating cycles of instability (Habibyar & Noorani, 2023; Byrd & Noorani, 2014).

The Taliban's return to power in August 2021, following the withdrawal of United States and NATO forces, marked a decisive turning point. Deprived of international aid and confronting frozen foreign reserves, the Taliban administration turned to mineral wealth as one of the few available instruments for economic recovery and international engagement. Within this context, China emerged as the principal external actor willing to engage, offering investment and infrastructure through the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) without the political conditionalities attached to Western assistance.

For China, Afghanistan represents both a strategic opportunity and a challenging frontier. The country's mineral endowment aligns with Beijing's broader industrial strategy to secure upstream supply chains for the energy transition and high-technology manufacturing. Regional stability in Afghanistan also serves Chinese security interests by protecting the country's western frontier and safeguarding investments in the China–Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). However, this engagement carries substantial risks given Afghanistan's fragile governance, persistent insecurity, and absence of regulatory frameworks.

This article examines how China's involvement in Afghanistan's mineral sector reflects the broader dynamics of global political economy under the BRI. It asks to what extent Chinese engagement promotes sustainable development and to what extent it reinforces structural dependency and asymmetrical governance. The central argument is that while China's approach diverges from Western neoliberal models in its means, it ultimately reproduces dependency through state-led extraction and geopolitical control. The promise of shared prosperity masks structural asymmetries embedded in the logic of global accumulation.

This inquiry carries broader relevance beyond Afghanistan. The intensifying global competition for critical minerals has generated new configurations of dependency, as states rich in these materials confront renewed extractive pressures framed in the language of sustainability. The concept of "green extractivism" (Gudynas, 2013; Riofrancos, 2020) captures this paradox: the pursuit of decarbonization can reproduce the same inequalities it purports to address. Afghanistan represents an extreme expression of this contradiction—a state with immense mineral potential that remains structurally trapped in underdevelopment.

The analysis that follows draws on policy documents, international institutional reports, and academic literature, complemented by semi-structured interviews with three Afghan policymakers and civil society specialists conducted in 2023. Section 2 reviews the relevant literature on the BRI and Afghan resource governance. Section 3 presents the theoretical framework. Section 4 maps Afghanistan's mineral landscape. Section 5 examines China's strategy within the BRI framework. Section 6 analyzes governance, dependency, and sustainability challenges. Section 7 addresses global value chains and technological dependency. Section 8 explores the human and local dimensions of extraction. Section 9 addresses the environmental politics of the green transition. Section 10 concludes with policy implications and broader lessons for the Global South.

Literature Review

Academic scholarship on the Belt and Road Initiative has generally organized around two analytical positions. The first emphasizes its developmental promise, highlighting infrastructure connectivity and the potential for South–South cooperation (Zhao, 2022; Brautigam, 2009). The second foregrounds concerns about debt dependency, geopolitical leverage, and governance deficits (Rolland, 2019; Gallagher & Irwin, 2020). Parallel literatures on Afghanistan's resources document the persistence of the resource curse and institutional fragility, demonstrating how mineral wealth tends to fuel corruption, conflict, and elite capture rather than broad-based development (Byrd & Noorani, 2014; SIGAR, 2015; Goodhand, 2004).

While these bodies of scholarship provide essential insights, they tend to treat Afghanistan either as a passive object of great-power strategies or as a fragile state isolated from global systemic dynamics. This article bridges these perspectives by integrating four distinct theoretical frameworks—Uneven and Combined Development, the Resource Curse, Dependency Theory, and Chinese state capitalism—into a unified analytical lens. Together, they enable a more comprehensive interpretation of how global structures and China's state-led capitalist model co-determine Afghanistan's mineral governance outcomes. This combined framework illuminates both the domestic vulnerabilities specific to Afghanistan and the systemic asymmetries that characterize the global political economy of the green transition.

The growing literature on green extractivism (Gudynas, 2013; Riofrancos, 2020; Siddi, 2022) provides an additional critical layer, situating Afghanistan's mineral future within global debates about ecological unequal exchange (Hornborg, 2019) and the justice dimensions of decarbonization. The EITI delistment of Afghanistan in June 2024 decision further underscores the collapse of the transparency architecture that had partially regulated extractive governance between 2009 and 2021, opening new questions about accountability in the current period.

Theoretical Framework

Understanding China's engagement in Afghanistan's mineral sector requires a theoretical apparatus that connects global structures to local conditions. Four frameworks guide this analysis: Uneven and Combined Development (UCD), the Resource Curse, Dependency Theory, and Chinese state capitalism. Together they explain how global capitalism simultaneously produces modernization and dependency—different faces of the same systemic process.

Uneven and Combined Development

The concept of Uneven and Combined Development (UCD) was originally elaborated by Leon Trotsky (1932) to account for the coexistence of different historical stages within a single capitalist system. Trotsky demonstrated that rather than homogenizing societies, capitalism combines advanced and archaic forms of production in complex and contradictory configurations. Subsequent scholars—notably Rosenberg (2016) and Anievas and Nişancıoğlu (2015) extended UCD to international relations, showing how global capitalism generates simultaneous patterns of advancement and stagnation across the international system.

Afghanistan provides a compelling illustration of UCD in operation. The country exhibits a sharp juxtaposition between capital-intensive industrial mining projects exemplified by the Chinese-operated Mes Aynak copper concession, and the widespread informal artisanal extraction that sustains livelihoods across rural provinces such as Badakhshan, Nuristan, and Khost. These dual economies are structurally interconnected: global demand for minerals sustains both formal and informal sectors, while weak governance enables actors to traverse and arbitrage between them. UCD thus frames Afghanistan not as a "backward" society awaiting modernization, but as a site where multiple temporalities of capitalism intersect and interact.

The Resource Curse

The Resource Curse thesis (Auty, 1993; Sachs & Warner, 2001) addresses the paradox that resource-rich countries frequently experience slower economic growth and weaker institutional development than resource-poor counterparts. Dependence on resource rents tends to foster rent-seeking behavior, corruption, and conflict, while crowding out productive investment. In fragile states, these pathologies are intensified: resource revenues become tools of political control and patronage distribution rather than engines of diversification.

Afghanistan displays many of the canonical features of the Resource Curse. Mineral rents are regularly captured by elites and armed actors; the absence of transparency undermines public accountability; and foreign companies operating under opaque contractual arrangements tend to prioritize extraction speed over local reinvestment. The volatility of global commodity prices further undermines long-term planning. The result is extraction without transformation—a configuration in which mineral wealth reinforces rather than alleviates structural poverty. The Taliban government's delistment from the Extractive Industries

Transparency Initiative (EITI) in June 2024 has removed one of the few remaining accountability mechanisms, deepening this structural vulnerability.

Dependency Theory and Unequal Exchange

Dependency Theory, elaborated by Latin American scholars including Dos Santos (1970), Marini (1973), and Cardoso and Faletto (2010), situates underdevelopment within the global capitalist system rather than within the internal characteristics of peripheral societies. Peripheral economies are structurally integrated into world markets in ways that subordinate their production to the interests of core economies. Unequal exchange occurs when surplus value generated in the periphery is systematically transferred to the center through mechanisms of trade, finance, technology monopoly, and commodity pricing.

In Afghanistan, these mechanisms of dependency are clearly visible. Foreign control over extraction, technological reliance on external actors, and the absence of industrial linkages ensure that value chains remain externally oriented. Contracts awarded to Chinese firms such as MCC and Jiangxi Copper allocate ownership and operational authority to external actors while Afghanistan supplies raw materials, labor, and sovereign concessions. The country's dependency is not merely economic but geopolitical: its strategic location attracts competing powers that deploy economic instruments primarily to secure their own influence rather than to promote Afghan development (Byrd & Noorani, 2014; author interviews, 2023).

Chinese State Capitalism

The rise of Chinese state capitalism has profoundly reshaped the global political economy. Unlike neoliberal globalization, which prioritizes private capital and market liberalization, Chinese state capitalism combines state ownership, strategic planning, and international expansion through state-owned enterprises (SOEs) and policy banks (Naughton & Tsai, 2015). The BRI institutionalizes this model by integrating infrastructure, trade, and investment into a coherent geopolitical strategy.

The "Beijing Consensus" (Ramo, 2004) emphasizing stability, infrastructure development, and non-interference is attractive to many developing countries precisely because it avoids the political conditionalities attached to Western aid. However, this model also reproduces hierarchical dependency by embedding peripheral economies into Chinese-controlled value chains. The BRI's infrastructure-for-resources logic typically limits local autonomy and creates new forms of structural dependency under a state-capitalist rather than a market-liberal framework.

Table 1 synthesizes the four theoretical perspectives, highlighting their core mechanisms and empirical manifestations in Afghanistan's mineral economy.

Table 1 — Theoretical Framework for Analyzing Structural Dependency in Afghan Mineral Sector

Theoretical Perspective	Core Logic / Mechanism	Manifestation in Afghan Context
Uneven and Combined Development (UCD)	Coexistence and interaction of advanced and archaic economic forms within global capitalism	Juxtaposition of capital-intensive industrial mining (Mes Aynak) with widespread artisanal and informal extraction in Badakhshan, Nuristan, and Khost.
Resource Curse	Resource rents undermine governance, foster corruption, and weaken institutions	Elite capture of mineral revenues; weak Ministry of Mines oversight; informal taxation by local commanders; EITI delistment (2024).
Dependency Theory	Peripheral economies are structurally integrated into global markets in subordinate roles	Reliance on Chinese firms (MCC, Jiangxi Copper, CAPEIC) for capital, technology, and operational control; export of unprocessed minerals; externally controlled value chains.
Chinese State Capitalism	State-led, strategically coordinated global expansion via SOEs and the BRI	Chinese SOEs shape extractive rules, secure long-term access, and channel infrastructure toward export corridors, embedding Afghanistan in China-centric value chains.

Convergence of All Four Frameworks	Mutually reinforcing mechanisms of structural domination	Produces structural dependency and asymmetrical governance, severely limiting prospects for autonomous, sustainable, and diversified development.
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Source: Elaborated by the author based on Trotsky (1932), Rosenberg (2016), Anievas & Nişancıoğlu (2015), Auty (1993), Sachs & Warner (2001), Dos Santos (1970), Marini (1973), Cardoso & Faletto (2010), Naughton & Tsai (2015), Ramo (2004), Rolland (2019), Byrd & Noorani (2014), SIGAR (2015), USGS (2011), author interviews (2023).

Afghanistan's Mineral Landscape

To grasp why Afghanistan has become central to global mineral geopolitics, it is essential to map the scale and spatial distribution of its geological endowment. Soviet geological surveys conducted during the 1970s and 1980s identified more than 1,400 mineral occurrences. Subsequent assessments by the USGS (2011) confirmed vast reserves of copper, iron, lithium, gold, chromite, and rare earth elements. These resources are concentrated in several key provinces: Logar (Mes Aynak copper), Bamyan and Baghlan (Hajigak iron ore), Helmand and Ghazni (lithium-bearing pegmatites), and Nuristan and Kunar (rare earth elements and gemstones). Collectively, these deposits represent an extraordinary potential for economic transformation—potential that has remained systematically unrealized due to conflict, governance failure, and infrastructural deficits.

The development trajectory of Afghanistan's mining sector has always been entangled with political instability. During the Soviet occupation (1979–1988), geological mapping expanded significantly and gas extraction at Shiberghan reached industrial scale—representing the highest level of mining activity in the country's modern history. However, large-scale metal mining did not materialize. After the Soviet withdrawal, the subsequent civil war (1989–1996) reduced the sector to artisanal subsistence levels. Following the US-led intervention in 2001, international donors and private investors briefly viewed mining as a potential anchor for reconstruction. The 2008 contract for the Mes Aynak copper deposit, awarded to China Metallurgical Group Corporation (MCC) at an estimated value of approximately 2.8 billion US dollars, represented the largest single foreign investment in Afghan history. Security challenges, the discovery of a major Buddhist archaeological site, corruption in the licensing process, and disputes over infrastructure obligations delayed the project indefinitely (SIGAR, 2015; Byrd & Noorani, 2014).

Since returning to power in August 2021, the Taliban administration has actively sought to attract mineral investment to offset economic isolation and the loss of approximately 9.5 billion dollars in frozen foreign reserves. In January 2024, the Ministry of Mines and Petroleum signed a 540-million-dollar oil extraction deal with the Xinjiang Central Asia Petroleum and Gas Company (CAPEIC), a subsidiary of CNPC (Dawi, 2024). Taliban leadership has also signaled openness to lithium extraction partnerships with Chinese firms including CATL and TBEA. However, decision-making remains highly centralized and opaque, reflecting continuities with pre-2021 governance patterns: as documented by Byrd and Noorani (2014) and reaffirmed in field interviews conducted in 2023, local commanders continue to exercise autonomous fiscal authority over informal mining operations, collecting taxes independently and reinforcing administrative fragmentation.

Mining activities in Afghanistan carry severe environmental and social risks. The Mes Aynak project has already displaced communities in the Mohammad Agha district and generated documented concerns about pollution of the Logar River (Rahmati, 2024). Lithium extraction in Helmand threatens to worsen acute water scarcity in one of the country's most arid regions. Artisanal mining operations in Badakhshan and Nuristan have destroyed riverbeds and forest cover while involving child labor and dangerous working conditions. These challenges expose enduring tensions between global sustainability rhetoric and local extractive realities.

China's Strategy and the Belt and Road Initiative

China's engagement in Afghanistan cannot be analyzed in isolation from the broader ambitions of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), which seeks to restructure global economic and geopolitical linkages through infrastructure and connectivity spanning Asia, Africa, and Europe (Rolland, 2019). The BRI is simultaneously an economic project and a geopolitical vision: it aims to secure upstream supply chains, open new markets for Chinese exports, and expand Beijing's regional and global influence. Although

Afghanistan is not a formal BRI member state, its geographic position between CPEC and the Central Asian corridors makes it a peripheral but symbolically important node in this larger architecture.

China's engagement operates primarily through a network of state-owned enterprises (SOEs) that serve both commercial and strategic objectives. Firms including MCC, Jiangxi Copper, CNPC, and its subsidiary CAPEIC function as extensions of national industrial policy. These enterprises receive financing from policy banks—notably the China Development Bank and the Export–Import Bank of China—and operate under the strategic coordination of the National Development and Reform Commission (NDRC) and the Ministry of Commerce. This institutional architecture allows China to pursue extractive objectives with a degree of coordination and risk tolerance that private actors cannot replicate.

Beijing frames its engagement through what it describes as the "security–development nexus" (NDRC, 2015): the proposition that economic growth fosters stability, which in turn enables investment and regional connectivity. In practice, this framework has proven inadequate in Afghanistan. The repeated delays of Mes Aynak—driven by persistent insecurity, local opposition, and institutional dysfunction—demonstrate that investment without political legitimacy cannot guarantee stability. China has consequently adopted a cautious strategy that minimizes capital exposure while maintaining geopolitical presence. It has appointed an ambassador to Kabul and engaged in high-level economic discussions with the Taliban, without extending formal diplomatic recognition.

Infrastructure built under BRI logic functions primarily as extractive connectivity: roads and potential rail links are designed to channel minerals from deposits to export routes rather than to integrate mines into the domestic economy. Proposed projects such as the Five Nations Railway—linking China, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Afghanistan, and Iran—and potential road corridors connecting Afghanistan to CPEC would embed the country within a Chinese-managed logistical system that serves Beijing's industrial priorities rather than Afghan development needs (Rolland, 2019). This spatial reconfiguration of Afghanistan's economic geography reproduces enclave economies and limits local value capture.

Table 2 summarizes the key differences between Western neoliberal and Chinese state-capitalist investment models, contextualizing Afghanistan's experience within a comparative framework.

Table 2 — Comparison of Investment Models: Western Neoliberal vs. Chinese State-Capitalist (BRI)

Feature	Western Neoliberal Model	Chinese State-Capitalist Model (BRI)
Primary Actor	Private corporations; IMF / World Bank	State-owned enterprises (SOEs); policy banks (CDB, Exim Bank)
Conditionalities	Political and governance reforms; fiscal austerity	Non-interference; political neutrality
Focus	Market liberalization; privatization	Infrastructure-for-resources; connectivity corridors
Value Chain Control	Downstream (technology, branding, consumer markets)	Upstream (extraction) to midstream (processing)
Outcome for Host Country	Fiscal austerity; structural policy reform conditionality	Infrastructure and employment, but structural dependency (context-specific)
Afghanistan Example	USAID/TFBSO mining programs (2002–2014)	Mes Aynak (MCC); CAPEIC oil deal (2024); proposed lithium partnerships

Source: Elaborated by the author based on Williamson (1994), Stiglitz (2002), Harvey (2005), Brautigam (2009), Naughton & Tsai (2015), Rolland (2019), Pike (2020), SIGAR (2015), Dawi (2024).

Governance, Dependency, and Sustainability Challenges

Afghanistan's governance institutions remain severely fragmented and under-resourced. The Ministry of Mines and Petroleum is chronically understaffed, lacks qualified technical personnel, and has minimal auditing capacity. Licensing and contract management processes are structurally exposed to political interference. Local commanders and regional power brokers systematically impose informal taxation on mining operations, undermining whatever authority central institutions nominally hold (Byrd & Noorani, 2014; author interviews, 2023). These conditions foster rentier dynamics in which political legitimacy is

sustained through the patronage distribution of resource rents rather than through productive public investment.

The delisting of Afghanistan from the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (EITI) in June 2024, formalized through decision has removed the principal multilateral accountability framework that had partially regulated revenue reporting between 2009 and 2021. This institutional collapse deepens the structural vulnerability of Afghan citizens to elite capture of mineral revenues and removes an important signal of governance credibility for potential investors seeking to distance themselves from reputational risks.

Environmental degradation constitutes one of the most acute development challenges associated with extraction. Mining activities in Logar province have polluted the Logar River, affecting irrigation systems and household water supply for communities downstream (Rahmati, 2024). Unregulated artisanal operations in Badakhshan and Nuristan have destroyed forest cover and degraded riverbeds. Prospective lithium extraction in Helmand threatens to exacerbate severe water scarcity in a region already experiencing chronic drought. These environmental pressures interact with deep social vulnerability: displaced communities lose access to agricultural land, water resources, and established livelihoods.

China's governance model in extractive sectors emphasizes centralized bureaucratic coordination and rapid implementation. In the Afghan context, this approach aligns with the Taliban's authoritarian governance style, producing a decision-making environment where contracts are negotiated without public consultation, parliamentary oversight, or civil society participation. While this alignment may facilitate project execution in the short term, it systematically undermines legitimacy and long-term sustainability. China's principle of non-interference operationally permits local elites to govern extractive revenues without accountability, externalizing social and ecological costs onto communities with no recourse.

Global Value Chains, Critical Minerals, and Technological Dependency

The growing global demand for critical minerals has transformed the geography of production, trade, and geopolitical power. The rise of renewable energy infrastructure, electric mobility, and advanced digital technologies has reoriented global value chains toward the materials that underpin them. This transformation has elevated countries such as Afghanistan, the Democratic Republic of Congo, Bolivia, and Kazakhstan from peripheral resource suppliers to strategic nodes in an emerging resource geopolitics. China occupies a dominant position in these chains: it refines approximately sixty percent of the world's lithium and over eighty percent of rare earth elements (IEA, 2023), giving Beijing structural leverage over downstream industries that position it as the indispensable intermediary between resource producers and global markets.

Global value chain (GVC) theory (Gereffi & Fernandez-Stark, 2016) demonstrates how value within these chains accrues not at the point of primary extraction but at the stages of processing, component manufacturing, and technology integration. For every dollar earned from exporting unprocessed minerals, substantially higher multiples are captured by firms controlling refining technology and market access. Afghanistan's participation in global value chains remains anchored at the extractive stage, with minimal domestic processing capacity and no industrial linkages. This positioning reproduces what development economists describe as the "commodity trap"—specialization in unprocessed raw materials that inhibits diversification and industrial upgrading (Gereffi & Fernandez-Stark, 2016).

According to AidData (2025), the political economy of critical minerals is increasingly shaped by financialization: prices for lithium, cobalt, and nickel are driven by speculative trading and futures markets that allow investors to profit from volatility while producer countries lacking sovereign stabilization mechanisms—absorb the risks. China's policy banks and SOEs deploy long-term off-take agreements and pre-purchase arrangements to secure mineral supplies at negotiated prices, insulating Chinese industries from global price surges while providing Afghanistan with only short-term and fixed-price revenue streams. These contractual structures systematically disadvantage Afghan counterparts, who lack the financial expertise, institutional capacity, and legal resources to negotiate equitable terms.

Table 3 documents the core features of Chinese mineral contracts across selected BRI partner states, revealing a consistent pattern of minimal technology transfer, constrained local value capture, and asymmetric fiscal arrangements.

Table 3 — Core Features of Chinese Mineral Contracts in Selected BRI States

Country	Key Mineral	Revenue Model	Local Content	Technology Transfer
Afghanistan	Lithium, copper	Fixed royalties; pre-negotiated long-term off-take prices (AidData, 2025)	Very low; reliance on imported labor and machinery	Minimal; raw material export orientation
Zambia	Copper	Royalties with tax holidays favoring SOEs	Limited enforcement of local hiring quotas	Basic operational training only; no high-tech transfer (Tull, 2021)
DRC	Cobalt / Copper	Resource-backed loans repaid via mineral exports	Local labor confined to low-skill roles	No domestic control over processing plants
Kazakhstan	Uranium / REEs	Joint ventures with SOE pricing influence	Higher local content but supplier chains China-oriented	Partial transfer within joint-venture structure
Pakistan	Copper / Gold	High profit repatriation; limited royalties	Uneven implementation of hiring commitments	No domestic refining capacity developed (Pike, 2020)

Source: Compiled by the author based on SIGAR (2015), Tull (2021), Byrd & Noorani (2014), Pike (2020), UNEP (2023), AidData (2025), and publicly available mining governance reports.

For China, withholding advanced technology serves a clear strategic purpose: it maintains hierarchical control within the value chain and ensures long-term dependency. This pattern corresponds to what Lall (1992) described as "controlled technology transfer"—operational know-how is shared to enable extraction, but core intellectual property and refining technology are retained. The absence of technical universities and geological research institutes in Afghanistan compounds this problem: without institutions capable of training specialists in mining engineering and metallurgy, the country cannot develop the expertise required to negotiate equitable contracts or exercise meaningful environmental oversight.

The Human and Local Dimension: Community Resistance, Adaptation, and Everyday Extractive Realities

Although Afghanistan's mineral sector is typically analyzed through the lens of state actors and geopolitical competition, extraction is equally shaped by dynamics at the community and informal-institutional levels. Local populations, artisanal miners, and non-state authorities actively negotiate, resist, and adapt to extractive projects in ways that complicate top-down narratives of state-led modernization.

The Mes Aynak project illustrates how community resistance can materially shape extractive outcomes. Beyond the well-documented constraints of insecurity and archaeological discovery, project delays were driven in significant part by disputes over land rights, inadequate compensation, and environmental risk. Residents of the Mohammad Agha district contested valuations of orchards, grazing land, and family homes, arguing that offered payments did not reflect post-conflict market values (Byrd & Noorani, 2014). Concerns about reduced irrigation flows from proposed water diversion for mining operations generated sustained opposition (Rahmati, 2024). Documentation by Integrity Watch Afghanistan (2016) records recurring tensions between communities and operators across the country, particularly where projects threaten ancestral land tenure or water access.

Artisanal and small-scale mining reveals additional dimensions of complexity. In provinces including Badakhshan, Nuristan, and Khost, artisanal miners negotiate informal taxation and security arrangements with Taliban commanders, local strongmen, and village shuras (SIGAR, 2015). These arrangements function as meso-level governance systems—providing access, dispute resolution, and degrees of predictability in the absence of coherent state oversight. Some mining communities have formed informal cooperatives, pooling resources to purchase equipment or negotiate collectively with armed actors (Pain, 2006). These informal networks are simultaneously embedded in global commodity chains: traders linked to Chinese intermediaries purchase lithium-bearing minerals directly from artisanal diggers in Ghazni and

Nuristan, integrating local extraction into international supply chains without formal licensing or regulatory supervision (UNEP, 2023).

The social consequences of extraction carry pronounced gendered dimensions. Environmental degradation—particularly water contamination and scarcity near mining sites disproportionately affects women, who bear primary responsibility for household water collection in most rural Afghan communities. In Logar, declining water quality near the Mes Aynak site has increased women's labor burdens and reduced time available for education and income generation (AREU & Pain, 2012). The arrival of transient male labor forces in informal mining zones, particularly in Badakhshan, has heightened insecurity for women and girls, contributing to harassment and reinforcing pressures toward early marriage (UNEP, 2023). In Helmand, preliminary lithium exploration threatens household kitchen gardens frequently managed by women, one of the few accessible sources of supplementary income. These patterns correspond to broader critiques of green extractivism, in which resource exploitation justified by global sustainability goals reproduces longstanding social and environmental inequalities (Gudynas, 2013; Riofrancos, 2020).

Environmental Politics and the Green Transition

The global transition toward renewable energy depends fundamentally on intensive mineral extraction. Technologies including electric vehicles, wind turbines, and grid-scale energy storage require vast quantities of lithium, cobalt, nickel, and rare earth elements. While the energy transition is framed as a pathway to sustainability, it relies on an extractive model that reproduces old hierarchies between industrialized and resource-producing regions—what critics have termed "green extractivism" (Gudynas, 2013; Riofrancos, 2020).

The concept of ecological unequal exchange (Hornborg, 2019) explains how environmental burdens are systematically transferred from wealthy to poorer nations through the global commodities trade. High-income economies import raw materials and effectively export pollution and ecological disruption, maintaining their own sustainability at the expense of peripheral ecosystems. Afghanistan's potential integration into global lithium supply chains exemplifies this dynamic: the country would export raw materials for batteries manufactured in China, Japan, and Europe, while bearing the full environmental costs of extraction domestically. This exchange operates not only spatially but temporally—future Afghan generations will inherit degraded landscapes, diminished water resources, and contaminated soils, while the short-term economic gains accrue primarily to elites and foreign investors.

China's BRI has incorporated environmental rhetoric through its "Green BRI" guidelines (2019), which formally commit to ecological protection and renewable energy integration. However, empirical assessments reveal a persistent gap between policy commitment and implementation (Li & Shapiro, 2020). In Afghanistan, environmental governance is effectively absent: the Taliban administration lacks comprehensive environmental legislation, impact assessment requirements, or community consultation mechanisms. Chinese SOEs consequently operate in a regulatory vacuum, with minimal accountability for ecological or social consequences.

Postcolonial environmental theory highlights how global environmental governance frameworks can reproduce power asymmetries while claiming universality (Nixon, 2011). Sustainable development narratives frequently reflect the perspectives of industrialized states and multilateral institutions, marginalizing local knowledge systems and community rights. In Afghanistan, extraction projects override customary environmental management practices without consultation or compensation. Environmental justice frameworks—which emphasize the principles of recognition, participation, and redistribution—are violated across all three dimensions: local knowledge and rights are ignored, communities are excluded from decision-making, and the distribution of benefits and burdens is profoundly asymmetric.

A just transition requires integrating ecological justice into the governance of critical minerals at both national and international levels. For Afghanistan specifically, this means rebuilding institutional capacity for environmental oversight, ensuring that affected communities participate meaningfully in project planning and impact assessment, and restoring transparency in contract and revenue management. Internationally, certification schemes, environmental compensation mechanisms, and structural reforms to global commodity pricing could help internalize the ecological costs of extraction and transfer a greater

share of value to producing countries. Without such redistributive reforms, the green transition risks entrenching rather than transforming the foundational inequalities of global capitalism.

Conclusion

China's involvement in Afghanistan's mineral sector encapsulates the central contradictions of contemporary globalization. Through the BRI, Beijing offers investment and infrastructure that appear to promote development, yet these engagements operate within a framework of asymmetric power and structural dependency. Afghanistan's extraordinary mineral wealth remains embedded in global production chains that primarily serve external industrial interests, while the local population bears the social, environmental, and institutional costs.

The integration of Uneven and Combined Development, the Resource Curse, Dependency Theory, and Chinese state capitalism into a unified analytical framework reveals how these patterns of unequal incorporation persist and reinforce each other. Afghanistan's mineral economy exemplifies modernization without autonomy, growth without diversification, and sustainability rhetoric built on unsustainable and inequitable extraction.

The environmental politics of the green transition add a further layer of complexity. The global race for critical minerals ties Afghanistan's future to the decarbonization agendas of distant industrialized economies, but the distribution of benefits and burdens remains deeply unequal. The delisting of Afghanistan from EITI in 2024 has removed a key accountability safeguard precisely at the moment when external extractive pressures are intensifying. Unless meaningful governance reforms and ecological safeguards are established an outcome that appears structurally improbable under current conditions, the green transition may replicate the injustices of the fossil-fuel era under a new ideological banner.

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